

VOICES FROM THE CLASSROOM: NON-NATIVE TEACHERS' STORIES OF INTEGRATING INDIGENOUS KNOWLEDGE SYSTEMS AND PRACTICES (IKSP) IN MULTICULTURAL EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

The integration of IKSP into formal education systems has garnered increasing attention due to its potential to enrich educational experiences, promote cultural preservation, and enhance community empowerment. Indigenous knowledge encompasses a wide range of traditional practices, beliefs, and wisdom passed down through generations within indigenous communities. This study explores the integration of Indigenous Knowledge Systems and Practices (IKSP) into the formal education system in DepEd Esperanza District III, Division of Sultan Kudarat, for the school year 2024-2025. The research, utilizing a qualitative ethnographic approach, investigates how IKSP integration can preserve heritage and shape future educational outcomes within Indigenous Peoples' (IP) communities. Fifteen IPEd teachers from secondary and integrated schools participated, meeting specified inclusion criteria. Thematic analysis was employed to analyze interview and Focus Group Discussion (FGD) data, ensuring ethical considerations were addressed. Findings indicate that the process of integrating IKSP into multicultural education is complex but transformative. Non-native teachers in IP communities face challenges such as language barriers, cultural misunderstandings, and trust issues with elders, compounded by socio-economic struggles among students. These barriers often hinder the effective transmission of IKSP, yet the rewards of fostering inclusivity, cultural respect, and empowerment in the classroom are significant. Teachers expressed the need for cultural sensitivity and inclusivity to create conducive learning environments for IP students. The study also reveals the varied strategies employed by non-native

teachers to navigate cultural and linguistic complexities. Based on the findings, the study recommends strengthening teacher preparation, providing culturally relevant resources, and institutionalizing IKSP in the curriculum.

Keywords: *Voices, Non-Native Teachers, Indigenous Knowledge Systems and Practices, Multicultural Education*

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

Integrating Indigenous Knowledge Systems and Practices (IKSP) into formal education systems has garnered increasing attention due to its potential to enrich educational experiences, promote cultural preservation, and enhance community empowerment. Indigenous knowledge encompasses many traditional practices, beliefs, and wisdom passed down through generations within indigenous communities.

However, non-native teachers face unique challenges and opportunities when integrating IKSP into multicultural education. Their experiences often highlight a journey of learning and adapting as they navigate the complexities of understanding cultural nuances, traditions, and values that are unfamiliar to them. Many find themselves bridging gaps between traditional teaching methods and culturally responsive approaches, striving to create lessons that honor and preserve Indigenous heritage while meeting academic standards.

Globally, there has been a growing recognition of the importance of indigenous knowledge and the need to incorporate it into formal education systems. Initiatives such as the United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples (UNDRIP) emphasize the rights of indigenous peoples to preserve, practice, and transmit their cultures, including their knowledge systems (United Nations, 2017). Additionally, various international frameworks, such as UNESCO's Global Action Programme on Education for Sustainable Development, highlight the significance of indigenous knowledge in promoting sustainability and cultural diversity in education (UNESCO, 2014).

The study aligns closely with the objectives of the National Cultural Heritage Act of 2009 in the Philippines. Enacted to safeguard the nation's cultural heritage and promote its appreciation and understanding, the National Cultural Heritage Act emphasizes the importance of preserving indigenous knowledge systems and practices (IKSP) as vital components of its cultural heritage (Republic Act No. 10066, 2009).

By integrating IKSP into Indigenous Peoples' Education (IPEd), the study contributes to preserving indigenous cultures and ensuring their transmission to future generations. This aligns with the National Cultural Heritage Act's mandate to protect and promote indigenous communities' diverse cultural traditions and practices, fostering a

deeper appreciation and respect for their cultural heritage within the educational system (Republic Act No. 10066, 2009).

In the Philippines, the Department of Education (DepEd) issued DepEd Order No. 62, s. 2011, which provides guidelines for integrating Indigenous Peoples' culture, history, and values into the K-12 curriculum. This order emphasizes the importance of recognizing and respecting the cultural diversity of indigenous communities and incorporating their knowledge systems into education. It outlines strategies for curriculum development, teacher training, and community involvement to ensure the effective implementation of the program (DepEd, 2011).

Region XII in the Philippines, on the other hand, is home to various indigenous communities, including the Blaan, T'boli, and Manobo peoples (National Commission on Indigenous Peoples, 2020). The NCIP survey shows these communities possess rich cultural heritage and traditional knowledge systems that have sustained them for generations. However, rapid modernization and external influences threaten the preservation of indigenous knowledge and practices in the region (Laviña, 2017).

While studies have shown the integration of Indigenous knowledge into education systems (Gonzalez, 2020), there is a gap in understanding the effectiveness and challenges of such initiatives, particularly in the Philippine context and Region XII specifically. Existing literature often focuses on theoretical frameworks and policy recommendations, with limited empirical studies evaluating the implementation and impact of IKSP integration in Indigenous education settings.

The study investigated the current status, challenges, and opportunities related to integrating IKSP into IPEd frameworks in the IPEd-implementing schools in Esperanza District III, division of Sultan Kud. By doing so, the study aims to preserve Indigenous cultures, empower Indigenous communities, and promote more inclusive and culturally relevant education for Indigenous learners. The study can also apply to educational management by promoting cultural diversity, community empowerment, sustainability, and informed policy development and implementation within educational systems.

Research Questions

This study explored the experiences of non-native teachers teaching IKSP Integration in Indigenous Peoples' Education curriculum in the specific context of DepEd Esperanza District III, Division of Sultan Kudarat, for the school year 2024-2025. It answered the following questions:

1. What are the lived experiences of non-native teachers in integrating IKSP into multicultural education in IP communities?
2. What challenges do non-native teachers encounter when incorporating IKSP into the teaching and learning process in IP communities?
3. How do non-native teachers address the cultural and linguistic complexities in implementing IKSP within a multicultural educational framework?

4. What insights and recommendations do non-native teachers provide to enhance the integration of IKSP into multicultural education in IP communities?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed qualitative research, specifically the ethnographic approach, to investigate how integrating IKSP into the IPEd curriculum in DepEd Esperanza District III, Division of Sultan Kudarat, can preserve the heritage and shape the future for the school year 2024-2025.

According to the University of Virginia (2015), ethnography is a qualitative method for collecting data often used in the social and behavioral sciences. Ethnographers collect data through observations and interviews and then use them to conclude how societies and individuals function. Instead of manipulating life in a lab, ethnographers observe it as it happens.

Respondents of the Study

Table 1 displays the qualifications of the participants based on the criteria set by the researcher prior to the selection of qualified informants of the study.

Table 1
Participants' Inclusion Criteria

Qualifications
Participants: 15 Teachers
<p>Current Employment Status</p> <p>- Participants must be regular Indigenous Peoples Education teachers of Department of Education (DepEd) Esperanza District III, Sultan Kudarat.</p> <p>Minimum Teaching Experience</p> <p>Participants should have a minimum of 1 year and above of teaching experience assigned to mountainous schools in DepEd Esperanza District III. Must have experience handling Indigenous Peoples learners.</p>

Willingness to Participate in Narrative Inquiry

Participants must be willing to share their personal experiences and motivations through narrative inquiry methods, including interviews.

The participants of this study were the selected fifteen (15) teachers who are assigned in Indigenous Peoples Education (IPEd) implementing schools, who qualify the inclusion criteria set by the researcher.

Sampling Technique

During this study, a purposeful sampling technique was intentionally utilized to carefully select the teachers in DepEd Esperanza District III, a division of Sultan Kudarat, who met the researcher's specified inclusion criteria established by the researcher.

Purposive sampling, or judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling, is a variant of non-probability sampling. In this approach, researchers exercise their judgment and discretionary acumen in selecting individuals from the population to participate in their survey endeavors (Alchemer, 2021).

This sampling method mandates that the researcher possess prior knowledge of the objectives underpinning this study to effectively pinpoint and contact eligible participants through online survey platforms (Ngag, 2023) The researcher resorts to purposive sampling to secure access to a distinct subgroup of individuals, whereby all survey participants are meticulously chosen based on their alignment with a specific demographic or criterion (Alchemer, 2021).

Research Instruments

In this study, a semi-structured interview was the primary investigative tool employed during the interviews and Focus Group Discussions (FGDs). This included documentation tools such as audio recorders and multimedia applications such as In Vivo to help the researcher transcribe the responses through thematic analysis and coding. The study investigated the effectiveness, strategies, outcomes, and challenges related to integrating IKSP in the IPEd curriculum in the specific context of DepEd Esperanza District III, Division of Sultan Kudarat, for the school year 2024-2025.

The researcher met the NCIP and the municipal Indigenous Peoples` Mandatory Representative (IPMR) in the target locale of her study. Interpretation of the results involved thematic analysis, which identified recurring themes, patterns, and insights related to integrating Indigenous Knowledge Systems and Practices (IKSP) in Indigenous Peoples Education (IPEd). This analysis was conducted systematically, carefully

examining the nuances and meanings expressed by participants during the In-Depth Interviews.

The findings were presented in a comprehensive report that outlines the key themes and insights derived from the data. This report included direct quotes from participants to illustrate important points and provide context for the findings. Visual aids such as charts, graphs, or tables may also present quantitative data.

Additionally, the researcher considered organizing a presentation or seminar to disseminate the findings to relevant stakeholders, such as educators, policymakers, and community members involved in Indigenous education. It provided an opportunity to discuss the implications of the findings and explore potential strategies for addressing the challenges identified in the study.

This instrument's credibility and suitability were validated through a rigorous assessment process overseen by a panel of experts with specialized knowledge in developing pertinent research instruments.

Data Gathering Procedure

To ensure the research's reliability, the researcher adhered strictly to a predefined set of procedures. The primary objective was to examine the role of language in IPEd to understand how language is integrated into Indigenous education, its impact on cultural preservation, and the challenges it encounters among IP schools in DepEd Esperanza III.

In the initial phase, the research diligently sought formal authorization from the Dean of the Graduate School of SKSU and the Division Superintendent of DepEd-Sultan Kudarat. This authorization was essential to obtaining permission for the researcher to conduct the study, emphasizing the importance of ethical considerations.

A secondary authorization letter was sent to the District Supervisor, explicitly requesting access to the specific data required for this research. A meticulously crafted survey questionnaire was developed, evaluated, and administered to the targeted participants.

The researcher employed a purposive sampling technique to select secondary school teachers as participants in this study carefully. Assuming strict adherence to established health protocols, the researcher conducted interviews and facilitated FGDs through face-to-face interactions.

Ultimately, the data collected from interviews and FGDs were systematically organized, comprehensively analyzed, and interpreted using the thematic analysis approach. This approach was expected to provide a deeper understanding of the issues under investigation.

Data Transcription Process

All gathered raw data from the participants through interviews and FGDs were transcribed using the transcription process of Kvale and Brinkmann (2009). By following these step-by-step processes, the researcher aligned their transcription approach with the guidelines outlined by Kvale and Brinkmann (2009). This rigorous transcription process ensured the trustworthiness and credibility of the qualitative data, which served as the foundation for the subsequent narrative analysis and the meaningful interpretation of the gathered raw data.

These categories were either drawn from established frameworks or custom-crafted to align with the study's objectives. To execute this analytical process, a series of vital steps were meticulously followed:

Step 1: Data Organization and Preparation. In the initial phase, all data sources, including interview transcripts, notes from FGDs, and pertinent documents, were thoroughly organized and prepared for analysis. This step ensured the structured arrangement and accessibility of the data (Braun & Clarke, 2019).

Step 2: Data Immersion. Subsequently, the researcher deeply immersed herself in the data by reviewing interview transcripts and FGD notes. This immersive process helped her understand the content and context inherent in the collected information (Nowell et al., 2017).

Step 3: Systematic Coding Process. The third step involved commencing a systematic coding process. Initial codes were generated by identifying meaningful segments or patterns within the data. These codes encapsulated fundamental concepts, ideas, or themes relating to the role of language in IPEd to understand how language is integrated into Indigenous education, its impact on cultural preservation, and the challenges it encounters among IP schools in DepEd Esperanza III in the school year 2024-2025 (Clarke & Braun, 2021).

Step 4: Clustering and Preliminary Themes. Following coding, the identified codes were clustered into preliminary themes based on shared meaning or relevance. This step established an initial framework for organizing the data (Vaismoradi et al., 2016).

Step 5: Theme Scrutiny and Refinement. Following this, the emerging themes and their corresponding codes were scrutinized and refined. Researchers ensured their coherence and clarity, making necessary adjustments as needed. Each refined theme was assigned a descriptive label that succinctly represented its content, facilitating easy identification and interpretation (Terry et al., 2017).

Step 6: Linking Data Excerpts. Relevant data excerpts, such as quotations or segments from interviews and FGDs, were selected and linked to the themes. These excerpts served as supporting evidence for the identified themes (Nowell et al., 2017).

Step 7: Thematic Analysis. Finally, the thematic analysis transcended superficial identification. Researchers delved into interpreting the significance and implications of each theme within the context of the study's objectives, ensuring a deeper understanding of the data (Braun & Clarke, 2022).

They identified patterns, correlations, and variations within the themes to provide a comprehensive understanding of the challenges and opportunities involved in implementing IPEd programs.

This meticulous and well-structured process of thematic analysis empowered researchers to investigate and comprehend the strategies systematically and approaches teachers employed in addressing the specific linguistic challenges faced by IPEd teachers and implementers. Ultimately, this approach yielded valuable insights contributing to the enhancement of intervention programs aimed at addressing the issues on the role of language in IPEd to understand how language is integrated into Indigenous education and its impact on cultural preservation among IP schools in DepEd Esperanza III in the school year 2024-2025.

Data Analysis

Within the framework of the study, the researcher focused on the role of language in IPEd to understand the impact, strategies, outcomes, and challenges related to the integration of IKSP in the IPEd curriculum in the specific context of DepEd Esperanza District III, Division of Sultan Kudarat for the school year 2024-2025. As elucidated by Frick (2011), this method involved the systematic classification of textual components, encompassing statements, phrases, and words into organized groupings or categories.

Written interview data was collected from the participants to determine the experiences and motivations of teachers in the essence of language in IPEd-revitalization, preservation and challenges of teachers in Esperanza District III, Division of Sultan Kudarat, who have experience teaching in the IPEd implementing schools. The in-depth interviews conducted for this research will be used to distill the most salient participant answers into overarching themes.

Scope and Limitations

The study's geographical scope was limited to Esperanza III, specifying where IKSP integration occurred within IPEd. It focused solely on this region, ensuring in-depth exploration and analysis of the IKSP integration's success within this context. The temporal scope of the study was delimited to the school year 2024-2025. The research centered on this specific academic year to capture the current implementation and effectiveness of IKSP integration within IPEd during this period. It aimed to provide a snapshot of this timeframe's initiatives, challenges, and outcomes.

The study concentrated on the successful integration of IKSP in IPEd within Esperanza III. It investigated the strategies, programs, methodologies, and pedagogical

approaches used to integrate IKSP into the curriculum. The research delved into the specific elements contributing to the success of this integration, such as teaching methods, community involvement, curriculum design, and learner engagement. It focused on key stakeholders involved in the IKSP integration within Esperanza III, including educators, administrators, learners, Indigenous community leaders, and relevant organizations actively implementing and supporting the integration of IKSP within IPEd.

The research was limited to Esperanza III and did not encompass IKSP integration in other regions or schools. Additionally, it focused only on the specific academic year 2024-2025, excluding analyses of previous or subsequent years. The study acknowledged language and cultural factors that may have impacted the interpretation and understanding of IKSP integration. It faced limitations related to language barriers or differing cultural perspectives that could have affected the research findings.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The integration of IKSP into formal education systems has garnered increasing attention due to its potential to enrich educational experiences, promote cultural preservation, and enhance community empowerment. Indigenous knowledge encompasses a wide range of traditional practices, beliefs, and wisdom passed down through generations within indigenous communities. This study employed qualitative research, specifically the ethnographic approach, to investigate the preservation of heritage and shaping future through the integration of IKSP in the IPEd curriculum in DepEd Esperanza District III, Division of Sultan Kudarat for the school year 2024-2025. The study involved a total of fifteen (15) IPEd teachers from among secondary and Integrated schools in DepEd Esperanza District III, Division of Sultan Kudarat, who meet the researcher's specified inclusion criteria. Thematic analysis was used to analyze the data from the interview and Focus Group Discussion (FGD). Ethical Considerations were also made in this study.

Based on the result, the integration of IKSP into multicultural education is a complex but transformative process for non-native teachers in IP communities. While challenges such as language barriers and cultural differences exist, the rewards of learning from Indigenous cultures and fostering inclusivity and respect in the classroom make this process profoundly impactful. The experiences of non-native teachers in integrating IKSP, as illustrated by the teachers' statements, reinforce the critical role of cultural sensitivity, inclusivity, and empowerment in creating a conducive learning environment for IP students.

Further, it was also revealed that teachers face multiple challenges in integrating Indigenous Knowledge Systems and Practices (IKSP) into their teaching. Cultural sensitivity is a significant concern, as misunderstandings of indigenous practices can lead to misinterpretation and confusion. Trust issues and generational gaps further complicate knowledge transmission, as some elders hesitate to share due to historical trauma, while younger students are more influenced by urban life. The rigid curriculum structure makes

it difficult to incorporate IKSP effectively, forcing teachers to balance standardized education with indigenous traditions. Additionally, a lack of support from elders or community leaders, often due to their availability or reluctance, poses another barrier. Finally, student engagement is hindered by socio-economic struggles and language barriers, making it challenging for teachers to sustain interest and participation in culturally integrated learning.

Furthermore, non-native teachers employ a variety of strategies to address the cultural and linguistic complexities inherent in implementing Indigenous Knowledge Systems and Practices (IKSP) within a multicultural educational framework. By contextualizing and indigenizing teaching materials, utilizing bilingual and multilingual approaches, collaborating with Indigenous elders and community members, adapting teaching methods to cultural values, and actively using Indigenous languages and community practices, these educators create a learning environment that respects and supports Indigenous learners. These strategies not only improve academic comprehension but also foster a deeper connection to culture, heritage, and identity, ultimately contributing to more inclusive and meaningful educational experiences for Indigenous students.

Finally, the insights and recommendations provided by non-native teachers offer a valuable framework for enhancing the integration of IKSP into multicultural education in IP communities. Deepening cultural understanding, adopting contextualized teaching approaches, fostering community collaboration, addressing resource and training gaps, institutionalizing IKSP in the curriculum, and nurturing Indigenous identity are essential steps toward inclusive and effective Indigenous education. Future policies and programs should focus on strengthening teacher preparation, increasing access to culturally relevant resources, and ensuring the sustainability of IKSP integration in national education systems.

Conclusions

The following conclusions were made in light of this study's findings:

The integration of IKSP into multicultural education requires a deep understanding of Indigenous cultures, traditions, and languages. Non-native teachers must develop cultural sensitivity to foster inclusivity and respect in the classroom.

Language barriers, generational gaps, rigid curriculum structures, and limited community support create significant obstacles for teachers. Addressing these challenges is essential for the successful integration of IKSP.

Strategies such as indigenizing teaching materials, collaborating with elders, and using multilingual approaches help bridge cultural and linguistic gaps, making education more meaningful and accessible for Indigenous students.

Strengthening teacher training, providing culturally relevant resources, and institutionalizing IKSP in the curriculum will ensure the long-term success of Indigenous education initiatives.

Recommendations

In the light of the findings, the following were recommended:

1. **DepEd** may develop a Comprehensive Indigenous Education Training Program that equips non-native teachers with culturally responsive pedagogies, emphasizing Indigenous Knowledge Systems and Practices (IKSP). This program should include immersion experiences in Indigenous communities, ensuring teachers gain firsthand understanding of cultural and linguistic complexities.
2. **District Supervisors & School Administrators** may establish Community-Led Curriculum Development Committees that include Indigenous elders, cultural bearers, and educators. These committees may co-create teaching materials and lesson plans that authentically integrate IKSP while aligning with DepEd's multicultural education framework.
3. **Teachers** may implement Collaborative Teaching Approaches by partnering with Indigenous culture bearers as resource persons in the classroom. This ensures accurate representation of IKSP, fosters respect for Indigenous traditions, and enhances student engagement in culturally responsive learning.
4. **Future Researchers** may conduct Action Research on Contextualized Pedagogical Strategies that explore effective methods for integrating IKSP into various subject areas. Research may focus on best practices in overcoming cultural and linguistic barriers, leading to evidence-based recommendations for policy and curriculum development.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Before commencing this study, it is essential to underline the critical significance of ethical considerations in research focused on the impact, strategies, outcomes, and challenges related to integrating IKSP into the IPed curriculum in the specific context of DepEd Esperanza District III, Division of Sultan Kudarat, for the school year 2024-2025.

To prepare for implementation, the plans and recommendations were presented to SKSU to ensure adherence to prescribed procedures and protocols. Consequently, the following ethical principles were emphasized.

Informed Consent. Before participating, explicit and informed consent was diligently obtained from all school heads involved in the study. They needed to comprehensively understand the study's objectives, methodologies, potential risks, and benefits (Creswell & Poth, 2018). Furthermore, participation remained entirely voluntary,

allowing participants to withdraw from the study at any point without encountering any adverse consequences (Israel, 2015).

Anonymity and Confidentiality. To safeguard the learners' identities and responses, rigorous measures were enacted to ensure anonymity and confidentiality. Rather than actual names, pseudonyms or codes were employed to uphold participants' privacy. The collected data was securely stored, with access restricted solely to the research team (Wiles, 2013).

Avoiding Harm. Delicate subjects, such as the challenges inherent in their roles, were discussed with meticulous consideration for the potential emotional and psychological impact on the participants. Strategies were implemented to minimize distress, and a support system readily assisted participants when needed (Liamputtong, 2020).

Researcher-Participant Relationship. The researcher maintained a professional and respectful rapport with the school heads. Any actions that might exploit or harm the participants were scrupulously avoided, ensuring their utmost dignity and respect throughout the research process (Orb, Eisenhauer, & Wynaden, 2001).

Data Protection. Data protection regulations and laws were unwaveringly adhered to in order to safeguard the personal information of the participants. Stringent measures were employed to ensure the secure storage and transmission of data (Saunders, Kitzinger, & Kitzinger, 2015).

Voluntary Participation. Participants were assured that their participation in the study was wholly voluntary and devoid of any form of coercion or external pressure (Bryman, 2016).

Researcher Bias. The researcher remained vigilant regarding potential biases that might influence data collection and analysis, upholding objectivity and transparency throughout the research (Merriam & Tisdell, 2016).

Institutional Approval. Before initiating the study, the researcher sought ethical clearance from the pertinent institutional review boards or ethics committees (Flick, 2018).

Honesty and Integrity. The research findings were reported truthfully and accurately, without manipulation or distortion, to align with preconceived notions or biases (Tracy, 2019).

Beneficence. The potential benefits of the research to educational practices and policies were thoughtfully considered, ensuring that the study positively enhanced the education system (Beauchamp & Childress, 2019).

Cultural Sensitivity. The researcher displayed cultural sensitivity by respecting local customs, beliefs, and practices within the research setting and refraining from imposing external values on the participants (Smith, 2021).

Inclusion and Diversity. The research design prioritized inclusivity and diversity, encompassing a broad range of implementations of Indigenous Peoples Education (Ngag, 2023). By diligently upholding these ethical principles, the study was carried out conscientiously and with due regard to the rights and welfare of the involved IP learners (Chilisa, 2020).

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